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Implementation of School Learning Action Cell in Umingan District II

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Abstract

Research indicates that Learning Action Cell (LAC) sessions are essential to teachers' ongoing professional development. Further research is required to characterize and identify the methods and obstacles involved in putting LAC into practice. The study investigates the implementation of LAC sessions in the district utilizing mixed method. There were 53 public elementary teachers and 22 participants who underwent interviews for the challenges they encountered in LAC implementation. Findings revealed that only one indicator which is fully implemented along Learner Diversity and Student Inclusion whereas other indicators that were implemented are Content and Pedagogy; Assessment and Reporting ;21st Century Skills and ICT Integration; and Curriculum Contextualization, Localization and Indigenization. Also, there were eight (8) extracted themes on the challenges encountered by the participants. These are time commitment, LAC implementation activities and LAC Plan; Non-participation to LAC session in online modality; overlapping of activities; redundancy of LAC topics; difficulty in internet connectivity; non-articulation of LAC session objectives, and difficulty in learning methodology and program addressing learners' needs. Ultimately, the analysis comes to the conclusion that the school implements its LAC sessions using procedures. The developed framework may be implemented in this regard. It is noteworthy that larger-scale research of this kind is required, with the aim of implementing and assessing the study's output in terms of its efficacy.

Keywords: *learning action cell, implementation, LAC session, framework*

Introduction

Modern society demands high quality teaching and learning from teachers. Teachers have to possess a great deal of knowledge and skills with regard to both teaching and assessment practices in order to meet those demands and standards of quality education. Effective teacher learning and professional development is important for student achievement. Teacher learning is a continuous process that promotes teachers' teaching skills, master new knowledge, develop new proficiency, which in turn, help improve students' learning. Previous studies have indicated that when teachers are effective classroom managers, their students achieve at a higher level and display more interest in the class subject matter.

Classroom management is essential to both teachers' education and teachers' professional development, it is crucial to keep teacher's knowledge up to date, so they can deliver high quality teaching. Interestingly, we know very little about teachers leaching, considering that, teachers themselves are experts in teaching and learning. This paper explores this area, in order to shed a light on the importance of continuous development program for teachers' learning. The government is doing its best to improve the teachers' performance. The Department of Education continues to find ways to improve the teaching-learning process by continuously capacitating the teachers so that they will be able to deliver the K to 12 Curriculum successfully. Likewise, when collaboration is effective and the model is sustained over time, there are specific changes noted in staff development.

It is important to note that the pandemic serves as a wake-up call for schools to be more critical and capable of unlocking their innate powers in delivering instruction in any format necessary to reach every student. By collaborating with others to assure student achievement and school progress, teachers become leaders both within and outside the classroom. Teacher leadership also considers the basic features of dispersed leadership theory: empowerment, autonomy, and participatory democracy (Kamaruzaman, 2020). Leadership is an interconnected discipline wherein the absence of one will not attain the addressed goals. It is in our best interests as teachers to deliver what is appropriate for our students in terms of knowledge and abilities. According to Arrieta (2021), education leaders, mostly teachers who function as instructional leaders, are the key drivers of the curriculum. As curriculum are enhanced through student-centered teaching, instructional practices, and school activity implementation with administrator support for teacher effective learning, continuing education, and succession planning were indeed essential for teachers to have clearly established and harmonizing activities by having given personal freedom to the individual to learn in the actual basis and elevated learning.

As stated in DepEd Order 35 s., with the Learning Action Cell. It was a professional development activity in 2016 that intended to enhance pedagogical competencies, instructional methodologies, and assessment processes through deliberate planning, improving school-based advancement, and cost-effective learning development. By decreasing workload and boosting workplace collaboration, Learning Action Cell (LAC) sessions improve instructors' overall happiness with their jobs, and this is a professional learning community in the form of a school to offer instructors support (Bajar, Bajar, & Alarcon, 2021). Each member of the teachers' organization is given the opportunity to grow and develop on their own when they are given the opportunity to learn and improve. The curriculum, as well as the teacher and school leaders, play a role in enhancing the quality of education. Teachers, as the leading reasons for accomplishing the curriculum's objectives, should make progress via professional development and continuous learning in order to help students accomplish academic performance.

The movement in curriculum from K to 12 curricula has a significant impact on teachers' methods, material, and expertise, as well as students' learning achievements. The Department of Education (DepEd) issued DepEd Order No. 35, s. that every public school is expected to keep Learning Action Cell (LAC) meetings (De Vera, de Borja, de Guzman, & Orleans, 2020). Moreover, to be successful and answering what are the needs-based for school progression, Learning Action Cell requires substantial thinking in responding to the needs of teachers toward students' academic accomplishment using this professional learning practice. Teachers collaborate in a learning action cell, which would be a learning circle that enhances professional development and encourages them into becoming agents for change (Binauhan, 2019). Furthermore, Vega (2019) stated that the Department of Education (DepEd) in the Philippines advises a wide range of professional development activities. Most of the mechanisms to strengthen teaching were presented as a top-down method, implying understanding is transferred directly or allowed to share by an experienced professional and afterwards allowed to pass on to teachers. This learning circle was a bridge in addressing the gaps and improving teacher's pedagogical skills. The Learning Action Cell was established to improve the teaching and learning process by addressing instructional gaps, supervision, and management, which contributes to conceptual learning on student achievement and teacher competence to instruct in order to attain the goals in the K–12 curriculum. Through the Learning Action Cell, it should maintain an open culture wherein challenges were acknowledged, and solutions are sought as a part of the school. It should also exhibit a commitment to see things very differently, engage in complex ways, and connect well with others (LAC). The Learning Action Cell (LAC) is critical in enhancing learning process by continually improving opportunities, attempting to keep teachers engaged, and captivating the others in becoming great teachers in the contemporary age (Madriaga, 2021).

Research Questions

This study aimed to explore the School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) as teachers' professional development in Umingan District II, SDO Pangasinan II for the SY 2022-2023. Specifically, it sought to address the following questions:

1. What is the level of implementation of the School Learning Action Cell of the teacher-respondents during SY 2022-2023 along with:
 - 1.1. Learner Diversity and Student Inclusion;
 - 1.2. Content and Pedagogy;
 - 1.3. Assessment and Reporting;
 - 1.4. 21st-Century Skills and ICT Integration; and
 - 1.5. Curriculum Contextualization, Localization and Indigenization?
2. What are the challenges experienced by the teachers in the implementation of School Learning Action Cell sessions?
3. What professional development framework as an intervention can be proposed in the implementation of School Learning Action Cell?

Methodology

Research Design

The present study employed a mixed method approach. The researcher utilized a sequential methodology, beginning with the acquisition and examination of qualitative data and subsequently on to the collection and analysis of quantitative data. Creswell (2013) posited that qualitative research encompasses various measures, including data organization, first archival review, transcription and concept arrangement, data indication, and analytic development. Using this design, the researcher had opportunities to study contextual factors such as the participant's experiences with the challenges in implementing the reading intervention. Remarkably, the qualitative part of the study used a descriptive phenomenological design, while the quantitative descriptive method was used for the quantitative part.

The descriptive phenomenological design developed by Edmund Husserl will be used in this study. Phenomenological research is employed to uncover the fundamental framework of collective essences pertaining to certain social phenomena (Worthington, 2013). This approach centers on an individual's encounter's intrinsic nature or establishment (Merriam, 2002). The primary objective of employing the phenomenological technique is to reveal the authentic and unadulterated encounter with the phenomenon being examined (Turunen et al., 1994). This study will discover and give meaning to the participants' lived experiences on the challenges they encountered in the implementation of Learning Action Cell. Through this, relevant data straight from the participants will be generated so that a timely and relevant training that could be drawn to help improve the professional development of teachers.

Within this perspective, this study utilized descriptive phenomenology or Eidetic following the works of Husserl. The researcher follows the four (4) steps in descriptive phenomenological Eidetic design: bracketing, intuiting, analyzing, and describing (Peres, 2017). First, the researchers identify preconceived beliefs and opinions about the phenomenon of bracketing. This is known as the epoche. The researcher's expectations and assumptions are bracketed prior to doing the analysis. Accordingly, the researcher wrote her own experiences regarding challenges experienced in implementing reading intervention. The researcher considers the phenomenon as free from prejudice and biases.

For the quantitative part, a questionnaire on level of impact of the School Learning Action Cell of the teacher-respondents in SY 2022-

2023 along with Teaching Strategies, Diverse Needs of Students, and Evaluation and Assessment was administered to the participants. Quantitative data will also be captured in the study using a quantitative descriptive design.

Thematic analysis was utilized in analyzing and interpreting data. The data generated from the in-depth interviews will be used to process and identify the presence of specific concepts and meanings through thematic analysis. Braun and Clarke (2012) stated that thematic analysis is a method for systematically identifying, analysing, or-ganizing, describing, and reporting themes found in a data collection. Findings from a thorough theme analysis can be reliable and enlightening.

In this study, each transcript was carefully read and examined while a marker was used to underline key phrases, patterns, and terms as patterns and themes emerged. From the explicit themes emerged, the data were dissected into contextual meaningful keywords. It was carried out by categorizing and coding the data.

Participants

The researcher conducted the study in Umingan District II, Umingan, Pangasinan. For the quantitative data on implementing the SLAC, 53 teachers were included in the study through a purposive sampling. This means teachers handling Grades 4, 5, and 6 were chosen as the respondents in the study. The distribution of the teacher participants is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Distribution of the Teacher-Participants

<i>School</i>	<i>Male</i>	<i>Female</i>	<i>Total</i>
Bantug E/S	2	1	3
Baracbac E/S	1	2	3
Cabangaran E/S	1	2	3
Cadiz E/S	1	2	3
Carosalesan E/S	1	2	3
Concepcion E/S,	1	2	3
Diaz E/S,	1	3	4
Don Alberto Vergara E/S	1	1	2
Don Montano Central E/S,	3	2	5
Gonzales E/S	1	3	4
Maseil-seil Aloo E/S	1	2	3
Nampalcan-Abot Molina E/S	1	1	2
Pangangaan E/S	1	2	3
Pemienta E/S	1	2	3
Ricos E/S	1	2	3
San Juan E/S	1	2	3
San Vicente Integrated School	1	2	3
Total	20	33	53

This study has three sets of participants: 53 teachers for the quantitative part and five teachers for the qualitative part. These participants were taken from grade 4, 5 and grade 6 levels. For the qualitative part, the study utilized in-person and online-focus group discussion as one form of rapid appraisal technique in gathering data. Purposive sampling was used to identify the qualified participants. Two respondents were beginning teachers and three seasoned teachers. They were chosen because they were behind in some areas of the teaching and learning process and needed more professional and technical assistance. These were the teachers handling key stage 2.

According to Rai (2015), the utilization of purposive sampling was justified based on its characteristics as a non-probability sampling technique. To ensure that qualitative data on the challenges of the implementation of SLAC is captured, inclusion criteria such as participants should be handling English, Math, and Science subjects, have handled the said subjects for at least two years, were elementary public-school teachers, and have experienced problems in implementing SLAC. While qualitative data on the challenges encountered by the teachers in implementing the SLAC was done through a focus group discussion. This data has driven the researcher to conduct the study at these levels since these teachers have been preparing the learners for they are about to enter high school. Lessons are becoming more complex in high school and require higher-order abilities. Thus, addressing this alarming issue in reading at grade 5 and 6 levels is necessary.

Instruments

Since the study followed a mixed method, qualitative data on the participants' challenges were collected through Online Focus Group Discussion (FGD) for the teachers and In-Person Focus Group Discussion for the teachers for the quantitative part (Yulianti & Sulistyawanti, 2021), while quantitative data were collected through a survey questionnaire.

In the qualitative part of the study, online focus group discussion (FGD) was utilized for a group of 22 informants, which is the maximum number of participants considering the data saturation points. The utilization of online focus groups has witnessed a notable surge in supplementing or potentially supplanting in-person research connections with technologically facilitated alternatives (Lobe, 2017).

Focus methodology was utilized that are most relevant when studying the challenges experienced by the informants in implementing the SLAC. Focus group discussion allows the informants to interact with one another rather than with the researcher of the study. Also, focus group discussion allows observation of how meaning is formed, questioned, explained, and disputed inside the group, providing insight into the interaction among informants (Morgan, 1996). A focus group discussion brings people with similar backgrounds or experiences to explore a particular topic of interest. Informants in focus group talks are free to converse with other group members; unlike other research methodologies, it encourages participants to converse with one another (Baral et al., 2016). In this study, the four stages in FGD will be applied: introduction, rapport-building stage, in-depth discussion, and closure. In the introduction stage, the moderator will be outlined the discussion's objectives, informed the confidentiality of the session, and introduced the participants. Informants are encouraged to start conversing and sharing by asking simple questions in the rapport-building stage. The moderator will be focused on the central questions in the topic guide, enabling participants to express their feelings and thoughts through conversation during an in-depth discussion. Finally, the moderator wrapped up the impressions or conclusions gathered, and participants clarified, confirmed, or elaborated on the information at the closure stage.

For the quantitative data, a survey questionnaire was used. Part I is on the level of implementation of SLAC along Teaching Strategies, Diverse Needs of Students, and Evaluation and Assessment. There were a total of 24 indicators that the participants must answer using a 4-point Likert scale: 5- Highly implemented; 4 means implemented; 3 Moderately Implemented ;2 means Slightly Not Implemented; and 1 means Not Implemented .

Also, the researcher prepared the research instrument subjected to content validation by pool of experts. Their comments and suggestions were incorporated and served as bases in the modification of the instrument. The revised questionnaire was tried out to teachers who are not included as respondents of the study for other comments and suggestions before it will be used for the final data collection.

The questions prepared was content validated by the five pool of experts involved in the validating team which comprised of two Principals, 1 Head Teacher, 2 Master Teachers.

Further, the average rating of the evaluators was computed to determine the content validity with corresponding descriptive equivalence. In this study, it was found out that the questionnaire is highly valid with a value of 4.68 which implies that the instrument covers all the areas needed in the study.

Reliability Analysis of the Data Gathering Instrument

The table presents the summary of the reliability analysis results. The instrument undergone reliability test to ensure the consistency of the results. Also, the questionnaire was administered to a sample of thirty (30) respondents in the districts. A test was used to measure the consistency of the test administered.

Cronbach's alpha measures the reliability, or internal consistency of the instrument. The computed Cronbach's alpha value for the level of implementation along with the given indicators obtained a value of 0.988. The Cronbach coefficient is above the 0.7 threshold which suggests that the instrument provides an excellent internal consistency.

Procedure

The following were the procedures taken in doing this study.

Initially, the researcher sought permission from the Schools Division Office of Pangasinan II to conduct a study about the Implementation and Challenges of SLAC in Umingan District II.

The collected data on the qualitative part of the study were on the challenges of implementing the SLAC; a focus group discussion was initiated with ten teachers as it reached the data saturation of the participants. The researcher employed purposive sampling as a method for selecting individuals. Informed consent was given to the participants, with ample time to review their study participation. After the consent was granted, the participants were oriented about the nature of the study, their nature of participation, their rights and benefits, and how the data were gathered from them be taken with the utmost confidentiality. The researcher prepared smartphones as recording devices, laptops, internet connection sources, journals, and pens ahead of time, as these are essentials for conducting the focus group discussion. During the FGD, the researcher informed the participants that the session was recorded using the agreed meeting tool and were asked for their permission. When the discussion is over, the researcher were expressed gratitude to the participants and assured them that the recorded interview will not be shared with anyone.

To gather the quantitative data, the researcher administered questionnaires through Google Forms to gather survey answers from the teachers. There were a total number of 53 responses.

When all data had been gathered, these were tabulated and treated. Finally, the treated data was analyzed and interpreted using statistical techniques reflected in the data treatment. Findings were written based on the results, and recommendations were crafted to address the problem under investigation.

Data Analysis

For the treatment of quantitative data, average weighted mean was used to determine and analyze the level of SLAC implementation during the S.Y 2022-2023.

On the other hand, it was employed the technique of thematic analysis (TA) as delineated by Braun and Clarke (2019). Regarding this matter, the researcher adhered to six processes in doing thematic analysis (TA): familiarization, coding, topic generation, theme review, theme definition and naming, and writing up. First, in familiarization, the researcher acquainted with their data by taking initial notes and getting familiar with it. Second, in coding, the researcher highlighted the sections of the text for an overview of the common meanings. Third, the researcher generated themes to identify patterns from the codes to formulate themes. Fourth, in reviewing themes, the researcher ensured that the themes will be valuable and accurate data representations. Fifth, in defining and naming themes, the researcher figured out how the themes helped them understand the data. Lastly, in writing up, the researcher accounted for the analysis of the data.

Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the results and discussion of the conducted study. The data presentation was done through tabulation that shows the frequency, percentage distribution, and other statistical treatments used to interpret the data. Tabulated and statistically treated data were the bases of the analysis and interpretation of this study.

Level of Implementation of the School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) Along Learner Diversity and Student Inclusion

The table presents the level of implementation of SLAC along learner diversity and student inclusion which is one of the core areas of focus for SLAC sessions.

Table 3. *Level of Implementation of the School Learning Action Cell of the Teacher-Respondents in SY 2022-2023 in terms of Learner Diversity and Student Inclusion*

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Teacher knows and cares for his/her students.	4.30	Implemented
2. Includes learner diversity and student inclusion in the LAC sessions.	4.70	Fully Implemented
3. Establishes learning environments that are responsive to learner diversity.	4.81	Fully Implemented
4. Teacher has knowledge and understanding of, as well as respect for learners' characteristics and experiences.	4.64	Fully Implemented
5. Caters diversity such as gender, community membership, religious beliefs, family configuration, and special learning needs.	4.62	Fully Implemented
6. Adjusts and differentiates their instruction to include all learners and to foster harmony in the class.	4.55	Fully Implemented
7. Provides remedial instruction for those who are experiencing difficulties in learning lessons.	4.32	Fully Implemented
	Mean	4.56
		Fully Implemented

Legend: 1.00-1.80, Not Implemented; 1.81-2.60, Slightly Not Implemented; 2.61-3.40, Moderately Implemented; 3.41-4.20, Implemented; 4.21-5.00, Fully Implemented

It is reflected in the table that the indicators along Learner Diversity and Student Inclusion in the implementation of SLAC was rated as fully implemented with an overall mean value of 4.56 which means that 81% - 100% level of implementation indicators along the given statements. The teacher-respondents regard they underscore the importance of learners' diversity and inclusion in which they included in LAC session topics and established learning environment responsive to learners' diversity. They were also knowledgeable and respectful for learners' characteristics and experiences; catered diversity; utilized differentiated instruction and provided remedial instruction for learners who are experiencing difficulties. However, one indicator which is implemented and that is the teacher-respondents knows and cares his/her students with a mean value of 4.30. Data denotes that effective SLAC implementation equips teachers with the knowledge and skills to create inclusive learning environments that cater to this diversity. The said findings are parallel to the study conducted by Binauhan (2021) in her study that assessed the performance of the teachers with regards to learner's diversity and student inclusion as very great extent. In addition, the implementers they performed very great extent in discussing that diversity emanates from a variety of factors such as gender, community membership, religious beliefs, family configurations and special learning needs.

Level of Implementation of the School Learning Action Cell in terms of Content and Pedagogy

The table shows the level of implementation of the School Learning Action Cell in terms of Content and Pedagogy.

It is noted in the table that the indicators of the implementation of SLAC along content and pedagogy obtained an overall weighted mean value of 4.10 which described as implemented. This reflected that about 61% -80% implemented the given indicators. Among these indicators are the teacher -respondents implemented developmentally appropriate teaching methods that addresses individual differences of learners; crafted learning goals in collaboration with students; mastered content and performance standards and learning competencies; planned with colleagues the weekly lessons and implemented for the specified time; translated curriculum content into relevant learning activities; contextualized the lesson to the learning needs of students. However, one indicator found fully implemented, and that is, teacher -respondents prepared lessons and executed lesson plans in the class with a mean value of 4.69. The above-mentioned findings implies that teachers implemented LAC in their schools and showed that they improved their professional

attributes, skills, and competencies in instructional delivery along content and pedagogy. It also indicated that in the findings, the teachers learned the value of collaboration and open-mindedness in the planning and evaluating the lessons during their LAC in schools. The findings of Binauhan (2019) and Madriaga (2020) supports these findings in which the LAC implementers vary great extent in implementing LAC along content and pedagogy.

Table 4. *Level of Implementation of the School Learning Action Cell of the Teacher-Respondents in SY 2022-2023 in terms of Content and Pedagogy*

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Prepare lessons and is relaxed in executing lesson plans.	4.69	Fully Implemented
2. Is able to implement developmentally appropriate teaching methods that respect the individual differences of learners.	4.10	Implemented
3. Can jointly craft learning goals in collaboration with his/her students.	4.16	Implemented
4. Teacher masters content and performance standards and learning competencies and deliver instructions effectively	4.08	Implemented
5. Collaboratively plan weekly lessons during the LAC and implemented for the specified time.	3.86	Implemented
6. Translates curriculum content into relevant learning activities.	4.06	Implemented
7. Teacher is systematic and contextualizes the lesson to the learning needs of students.	3.76	Implemented
Mean	4.10	Implemented

Legend: 1.00-1.80, Not Implemented; 1.81-2.60, Slightly Not Implemented; 2.61-3.40, Moderately Implemented; 3.41-4.20, Implemented; 4.21-5.00, Fully Implemented

As cited by Danguilan, (2017) noted that the first essential of effective teaching is that the teacher must have a thorough grasp of the subject he teaches. A highly effective teacher cannot simply learn the rudiments of the subject, master them thoroughly, and then stop. The highly effective teacher should master the content and performance standards and learning competencies and has a clear vision of what he wants his students to become.

Level of Implementation of the School Learning Action Cell Along Assessment and Reporting

The table shows the level of implementation of SLAC in terms of assessment and reporting.

It is reflected in the table that the level of implementation of SLAC of teacher -respondents in terms of assessment and reporting had an overall rating of 4.01 which means that the respondents implemented the indicators with 61% to 80%. Among these indicators, teachers provided feedback about learning outcomes; continually select, organize, and use sound assessment processes; and understood how to implement the learner-centered assessment policies of the K to 12 curriculums. Data implies that the indicators of pedagogical practices of teachers in terms of assessment and reporting focused on the above indicators needs to consider a full extent of implementation along designing and utilizing assessment strategies with curriculum requirements and reporting of feedback mechanisms to learners and stakeholders.

Table 5. *Level of Implementation of the School Learning Action Cell of the Teacher-Respondents in SY 2022-2023 in terms of Assessment and Reporting*

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Teacher understands how to implement the learner-centered assessment policies of the K to 12 curriculum.	3.89	Implemented
2. Discussions include ways in assessing the learning of students.	4.32	Fully Implemented
3. Provides feedback about learning outcomes	3.94	Implemented
4. Continually select, organize, and use sound assessment processes.	3.90	Implemented
Mean	4.01	Implemented

Legend: 1.00-1.80, Not Implemented; 1.81-2.60, Slightly Not Implemented; 2.61-3.40, Moderately Implemented; 3.41-4.20, Implemented; 4.21-5.00, Fully Implemented

In the study Verbo (2020), it is reiterated that the LAC sessions facilitated by a designated LAC leader, have proven to be effective in engaging a group of teachers in collaborating and solving shared challenges. Additionally, LAC sessions encourage critical reflection amongst teachers which increases the understanding and knowledge of the curriculum and classroom practices.

Level of Implementation of the School Learning Action Cell Along 21st-Century Skills and ICT Integration

The table below presents the level of implementation of SLAC in terms of 21st-Century Skills and ICT Integration of the teacher-respondents in Umingan District II.

Table 6. *Level of Implementation of the School Learning Action Cell of the Teacher-Respondents in SY 2022-2023 in terms of 21st-Century Skills and ICT Integration*

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Brings 21st century skills into the teaching and learning.	3.95	Implemented
2. Enrich lessons with simple integration strategies utilizing Information and Communications Technology (ICT) that are developmentally appropriate.	4.14	Implemented
3. Integrates ICT in instruction and assessment processes to make a more collaborative teaching and learning experience.	4.02	Implemented

Mean 4.04 Implemented

Legend: 1.00-1.80, Not Implemented; 1.81-2.60, Slightly Not Implemented; 2.61-3.40, Moderately Implemented; 3.41-4.20, Implemented; 4.21-5.00, Fully Implemented

It is depicted in the table that item statements that measures the performance of teachers in implementing SLAC along 21st-Century Skills and ICT Integration had an overall weighed mean value of 4.04 which described as implemented. Data implies that these indicators showed the implementation of 61% - 80% which means that the implementation of LAC focused on this area needs enhancement to be fully implemented. Among these indicators are enriched lessons with the integration Information and Communications Technology (ICT) that are developmentally appropriate teaching strategies; utilized ICT in instruction and assessment processes for a more collaborative teaching and learning experience; and adapted 21st century skills into the teaching and learning. These findings are unparallel to the study conducted by Binauhan (2019) which revealed that teachers assessed their manifestation of 21st century skills and they found it to be on very great extent. Also, the implementers justify there is very great extent in integrating 21st century skills into the teaching and learning situation with the highest weighted mean during the learning action cell implementation is stressed by Nudalo (2018) that when identifying the concept of innovative pedagogical practices, teachers of the 21st century must grasp that it refers to attempts to bring about reform in the classroom as well as the integration of technological resources that have sparked the emergence of the information society. Keeping up with the changes of the modern day, computers, audiovisual equipment, and other communication tools have gradually acquired a place inside educational institutions and in the process of changing pedagogical practice.

Eroles (2023) concluded in his study that the use of LAC sessions on shared pedagogical practices of seasoned and millennial teachers could really strengthen 21st century learning. It is also highlighted in his study that experienced educators can impart not only their subject-matter knowledge but also their wisdom, ethics, and tips on efficient classroom management. Teachers who are millennials can impart knowledge on 21st century skills and ICT integration, as well as how to be flexible and self-assured enough to adjust to the changes of the modern world.

Level of Implementation of the School Learning Action Cell Along Curriculum Contextualization, Localization and Indigenization

The table presents the level of implementation of Learning Action Cell in terms of Curriculum Contextualization, Localization, and Indigenization

It is noted on the table that the level of LAC implementation had an overall mean value of 4.20 which is described as implemented with a 61%- 80% of the indicators. Among these are focused on teachers linked new content to the local experiences that are familiar to students; modified teachers’ guide and learners’ materials to a particular locality; deepened curriculum contextualization through indigenization; made sure that the members of the community participate in indigenization processes and had time to discuss how their community linkages can support the curriculum and how LAC sessions promote their own professional growth. However, there are some statements that were rate fully implemented when teachers matched the curriculum content and instructional strategies relevant to the learners; considered individual differences in lesson planning and implementation; and identified and responded to opportunities linked to teaching and learning in the classroom, school community and other stakeholders.

Table 7. Level of Implementation of the School Learning Action Cell of the Teacher-Respondents in SY 2022-2023 in terms of Curriculum Contextualization, Localization, and Indigenization

Indicator	Mean	Description
1. Matches the curriculum content and instructional strategies relevant to the learners.	4.49	Fully Implemented
2. Considers individual differences in lesson planning and implementation.	4.33	Fully Implemented
3. Identifies and responds to opportunities to link teaching and learning in the classroom to the experiences, interests, and aspirations of the wider school community and other stakeholders.	4.63	Fully Implemented
4. Links new content to the local experiences that are familiar to students.	4.06	Implemented
5. Modifies Teachers’ guide and learners’ materials to accommodate the unique contexts of a particular locality.	3.94	Implemented
6. Deepens Curriculum contextualization through indigenization.	3.92	Implemented
7. Provides spaces for unique cultures in the K to 12 Basic Education Program.	4.22	Fully Implemented
8. Makes sure that the members of the community participate in indigenization processes.	4.17	Implemented
9. Finds time to discuss how their community linkages can support the curriculum and how LAC sessions promote their own professional growth.	4.05	Implemented
	Mean 4.20	Implemented

Legend: 1.00-1.80, Not Implemented; 1.81-2.60, Slightly Not Implemented; 2.61-3.40, Moderately Implemented; 3.41-4.20, Implemented; 4.21-5.00, Fully Implemented

Data implies that teachers implemented the process of contextualization, localization, and indigenization of the curriculum addressing the curriculum requirements to make it relevant and appropriate in the local context. As a matter of fact, teachers fully implemented the LAC in schools along learners’ differentiation and personalization aligned with the beliefs, culture, norms, and attitude of learners. It also shows teachers prioritize these aspects in LAC discussions focused on making the curriculum relevant to the local context. A contextualized, localized, and indigenized curriculum that considers the local context, integrates local knowledge, and respects indigenous cultures can lead to improved student learning that embodies constructivist approach.

This study confronts the study Basco et.al (2022) that teachers provide appropriate real-life situation and life patterns of the learners obtained the highest mean. In their studies, teachers allow their learners to learn the concepts using a constructivism approach. The study revealed that Science teachers facilitate teaching and learning process in line with the curriculum while they encourage the learners to be successful citizens in a changing local and global environment.

Similarly, this finding is similar with Ayaz and Şekerci (2015) where they claimed that the use of constructivist learning approach in different lessons and subjects has a high effect size for students' academic achievements, except the lesson of religious instructions. Hence, the constructivist learning approach can be used in almost all areas of teaching and learning process.

Summary of Level of Implementation of the School Learning Action Cell

The table shows the overall level of implementation of LAC activities in schools along Learner Diversity and Student Inclusion; Content and Pedagogy; Assessment and Reporting; 21st-Century Skills and ICT Integration; and Curriculum Contextualization, Localization and Indigenization.

Table 8. *Summary of Level of Implementation of the School Learning Action Cell of the Teacher-Respondents in SY 2022-2023*

<i>Dimension</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
Learner Diversity and Student Inclusion	4.56	Fully Implemented
Content and Pedagogy	4.10	Implemented
Assessment and Reporting	4.01	Implemented
21st-Century Skills and ICT Integration	4.04	Implemented
Curriculum Contextualization, Localization and Indigenization	4.20	Implemented
Mean	4.22	Fully Implemented

Legend: 1.00-1.80, Not Implemented; 1.81-2.60, Slightly Not Implemented; 2.61-3.40, Moderately Implemented; 3.41-4.20, Implemented; 4.21-5.00, Fully Implemented

It is depicted in the table that summary of Level of Implementation of the School Learning Action Cell of the Teacher-Respondents obtained an overall weighted mean value of 4.22 which is fully implemented. One indicator which is fully implemented along Learner Diversity and Student Inclusion obtained value of 4.56. Other indicators that were rated implemented are Content and Pedagogy (4.10); Assessment and Reporting (4.01); 21st Century Skills and ICT Integration (4.04); and Curriculum Contextualization, Localization and Indigenization (4.20). Data implies that the level of LAC implementation shows that LACs show potential in promoting collaborative practices but an opportunity for further development and support for teachers. Further, the conduct of LAC sessions with activities like discussions, presentations, or workshops. In general, LACs are a valuable tool for school improvement when implemented effectively. By addressing potential challenges and providing ongoing support, schools can leverage LACs to create a collaborative and growth-oriented teaching environment.

Stronge (2007) as reiterated by Medina, Lim & Camposagrado (2023) as cited in p. 2 of Article I. Rationale No. 2 of DO No. 35 s. 2016 identified factors to teachers' success that includes (1) good grasp of content which through learning objectives; (2) ability to select and implement the most effective instructional strategies and materials to cover content objectives; (3) ability to decide on instructional strategies based on formative assessment results; (4) focus on students' learning and holistic development; and (5) possess a strong professional and work ethics. The same was also considered in the study made by Garbe (2012) stressing the characteristics of effective professional development which impact teachers' progress and learners' development.

Challenges Experienced by the Teachers in the School Learning Action Cell Sessions

Based on the online interviews conducted among the twenty-two (22) participants, the researcher generated themes relative to the challenges encountered by the respondents in the implementation of LAC.

The data collected underwent data analysis through coding and theming. In this qualitative research, the responses from the selected participants were marked multiple times and in different segments. Therefore, the similarities among answers will be identified. The code set was then used for analysis and interpretation (Pritp, Naval & Carey, 2017).

In this regard, Table 7 presents the extracted significant statements from the interviewees and the emerging themes along devoted sufficient attention to instructional programs to achieve competency and curriculum criteria.

Table 9. Profile Along Devoted Sufficient Attention to Instructional Programs to achieve competency and curriculum criteria

It is reflected in the table that all respondents responded yes on the sufficient attention to instructional programs to achieve competency and curriculum criteria. The subthemes and extracted significant statements were shown below:

Table 9. *Emergед Themes on the Challenges Encountered by the Teachers in Implementing LAC*

<i>Subthemes</i>	<i>Responses / Extracted Significant Statements</i>
1. Professional Growth and Responsibility	Yes, because I need to meet the expectations of my school head. YES, I actively invest time and effort in learning, while achieving competency and curriculum criteria involves meeting the defined standards and expectations set by the educational institution or program.

	Yes, it's about professional growth and learning new ideas.
	Yes, it's about professional growth and learning new ideas.
2. Effective Teaching Strategies	Yes, as it serves as support that guides teachers like me to set instructional techniques, learning experiences, and to evaluate the students' performance in particular learning objectives and its outcome.
	Yes, to enhance and be familiarized with the teaching strategies.
	Yes, LAC sessions focus on instructional programs. The sessions I have attended were designed to explore and improve teaching methods, which directly impact my ability to deliver curriculum content effectively.
3. Student-Centered Focus	Yes, I am certain that we should give more attention in achieving competencies so that we could use this as a tool to help develop the skills and knowledge of our pupils.
	Yes, because it is important to achieving the competency and curriculum criteria. This will help understand what learners needed to learn, the methods in teaching, and also the assessment.
	Yes, devoting sufficient attention to instructional programs is crucial for achieving competency because it allows learners to engage deeply with the material, understand complex concepts, and develop necessary skills.
	Yes, it improves the quality of education and shapes the future of students.

Theme 1: Time Commitment

Teacher respondents value LAC as an invaluable tool for shared collaborative and professional practices that improved teachers' professional growth and responsibility; effective teaching strategies; and student-centered focus in providing optimum learning. It can be noted that the extracted statements showed the importance of LAC for improved teacher collaboration that encourage teachers to share best practices and learn from each other; Enhanced Teaching through LACs, teachers can develop new skills and refine their teaching methods; Focus on Student Needs that allows teachers to address specific student learning challenges identified through data; and curriculum development. It is through LACs that serves as platform for teachers to collaborate on contextualizing the curriculum to the local context.

However, it is also noted that teachers 'encountered challenge in implementing LAC due to time commitment. Scheduling regular LAC meetings is challenging for busy teachers. This finding is congruent to the the study conducted by Irinco et.al, (2023) revealed the challenges in conducting LAC session are the scheduling of the date and time wherein it has to be conducted, the availability of teachers as well as the funding. The extracted themes/ codes showed the schedule/time and source of fund.

Furthermore, the study of Ganiban (2023) corroborated the findings of the current study, which revealed that teachers' experiences with implementing LAC sessions emerged from their sharing. The first difficulty has to do with timing. Here, the participants discussed how challenging it is to schedule the LAC sessions given the availability of certain lecturers. Furthermore, they will not have enough time in the LAC sessions to fully comprehend and assimilate the material.

Management of Learning Programs and Content in LAC sessions that addressed the Instructional Gap

Table 8 displays the frequency and percentages of the Management of Learning Programs and Content in LAC sessions that addressed the Instructional Gap.

Table 10. It is depicted in the table that 19 or 86.36% of the teachers agreed with the management of learning programs that address the instructional gaps through LAC. The subthemes and extracted significant statements were shown below:

<i>Subthemes</i>	<i>Responses / Extracted Significant Statements</i>
1. Identification of Gaps	Yes, because LAC sessions can be used to address instructional gaps by identifying areas where learning isn't happening as effectively. However, the LAC implementation needs a harmonized framework based on the context of school.
2. Collaborative Strategies	Yes, LAC sessions provide a valuable platform for teachers to work together and ensure their students have the support they need to succeed.
	Yes, because in a training program, attendees will know how to cater to the instructional gap in everyone.
3. Sharing Best Practices	Yes, LAC sessions often involve identifying areas where teachers need improvement. This helps tailor programs to address specific instructional gaps. Most discrepancies between effective and ineffective instruction can be traced to the localization of content.
4. Critical Reflection	Yes, it's encouraged critical reflection among teachers.
	Yes, to be able to address any challenges about the learning process.
5. Focused Instruction and Discussion	Yes, seminars can be effective in addressing instructional gaps in learning. They provide opportunities for focused instruction, discussion, and interaction, which can help clarify concepts, reinforce learning, and fill in gaps in understanding.
6. Relevance of Content	Yes, because most discrepancies between effective and ineffective instruction can be traced to the localization of content. Learning would be more meaningful if the content is both relevant and

coherent with the students' needs and experience.
The implementation of activities of LAC needs enhancement.

Theme 2: LAC Implementation Activities and Localized Framework

Based on the above-mentioned table it is reflected that the subthemes emerged are identification of gaps; collaborative strategies; sharing of best practices; critical reflection; focused instruction and discussion; and relevance of content. In the implementation of the LAC session, conducting a needs assessment is the first thing to do. Here, the needs of the teachers, their classrooms, and their learners should be identified first through the conduct of needs assessment. Needs assessment is a part of strategic planning that helps in knowing and determining the essential targets and goals of every teacher. To support the claim, the verbalizations is cited: "Yes, because LAC sessions can be used to address instructional gaps by identifying areas where learning isn't happening as effectively".

The participants in the interviews disclosed that they use a variety of ways to conduct or carry out their LAC sessions. Discussions on the subject become insightful and original when a variety of tactics are used during the LAC session. These techniques make it easier for the teachers to comprehend the subjects covered in their LAC. According to Vega (2020), the purpose of the LAC session is to create a community of practice that participates in cooperative planning, problem-solving, and action implementation. Teachers can learn from one other and encourage one another during LAC sessions as they implement these changes in the classroom, as noted by Cartilla and Rondina (2020).

It is important to note, nonetheless, that the participants expressed how the LAC activities and framework were better implemented in the educational setting. This indicates that the process flow or contextualized framework that facilitates the proper, successful, and efficient execution of LAC activities in schools was the key component of the mechanism used to implement LAC sessions in schools. This validates the research done by Irinco (2024), which found that implementing activities centered around the LAC framework is the most barrier when holding a LAC session. Additionally, there was an issue with the participants' comprehension of the current LAC framework because they conducted FGD in place of LAC.

The study of Ganiban (2023), which detailed how schools use LAC sessions as a foundation for creating a localized framework, is consistent with the findings of the current study. The four (4) C's in implementing LAC sessions—doing needs assessment, designing the LAC session, coordinating for approval, and conducting LAC sessions through various strategies—were discovered through thematic analysis of the extended texts. These speak to the way the school conducts LAC classes. It's interesting to note that the participants' discussion identified three obstacles or issues with putting LAC sessions into practice: those pertaining to time, technology, and output. The outcome guided the formulation of the localized framework. Ultimately, the study finds that the school implements its LAC sessions using procedures. The developed framework may be implemented in this regard. It is important to note that larger-scale research of this kind is required, with the study's results being applied and assessed for efficacy.

Attendance to LAC Sessions in an Online Modality

The table shows the frequency and percentages of the participants along their attendance to LAC session in an online modality. It is reflected in the table that more than half of the participants attended LAC sessions whereas 9 or 40.91% of the participants did not attend LAC sessions through online modality. It implies that the non-participation of the other participants in LAC sessions posed a concern due to slow internet connectivity due to their geographical locations, equally important activities that the participant attend to, lack of resources, equipment and others. The subthemes and extracted significant statements were shown below:

Table 11. Attendance to LAC sessions in an Online Modality

<i>Subthemes</i>	<i>Responses / Extracted Significant Statements</i>
Effectiveness of Virtual Sessions	Yes, virtual LAC sessions can sometimes be less focused due to distractions and technical issues. Yes, virtual sessions can be less focused because of the lack of face-to-face interaction and difficulty in maintaining engagement.
Challenges of Virtual Learning	Yes, I find virtual sessions less focused because it's harder to stay engaged and there are more distractions. Yes, virtual LAC sessions are least focused due to challenges such as poor internet connection and difficulty in communicating effectively. Yes, virtual sessions are less focused because of technical issues and limited interaction. Yes, virtual sessions are generally less focused compared to in-person sessions because of the lack of personal interaction and engagement.
Adaptation and Adjustment	Yes, virtual sessions can be less focused, but we've adapted by using interactive tools and adjusting session formats to maintain engagement. Yes, although virtual sessions can be challenging, we've found ways to overcome distractions and improve focus through better technology and facilitation
Comparative Analysis	Yes, virtual sessions can be less focused, but we've adapted by using interactive tools and adjusting session formats to maintain engagement. Yes, I've noticed a difference in focus between virtual and in-person sessions, with in-person sessions being more effective due to better interaction and engagement.

Suggestions for Improvement	Yes, virtual sessions could be improved by providing better training for facilitators and implementing more interactive tools to enhance engagement. Yes, to improve focus in virtual sessions, we need to address technical issues and provide clearer communication channels for better interaction.
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Theme 3: Non-Participation to LAC sessions in an Online Modality

The above-mentioned extracted significant statements showed the subthemes on Effectiveness of Virtual Sessions; Challenges of Virtual Learning; Adaptation and Adjustment; Comparative Analysis; and Suggestions for Improvement. Extracted statements showed that their participants found out that virtual sessions are less focused, more distractions, slow internet connectivity, technical and communication issues, however they utilized interactive tools to make them engaged during LAC sessions. Also, the participants suggested the training of the facilitators for online modality. Data implies that the participants prefer face-to-face LAC sessions rather than online modality resulting to the non-participation of some participants in LAC sessions.

This finding confronts to the study conducted by Medina, Lim & Camposagrado (2023)

showed that pre-post survey results on Online LAC session planning is rated as moderately acceptable; implementation is ‘acceptable’; and evaluation is ‘moderately acceptable’. The teachers’ acceptability of Online LAC session practice increases after their participation in a fully online learning environment.

A thorough examination of the literature has shown how teachers view online continuing professional development (CPD) in relation to many contexts (social studies, literature, bilingualism, thematic response, design, and implementation) and effective PD features. The elements that influence acceptance rely on the type of online professional development program they have participated in, as well as its structure, tactics, and character. Even though there are elements of online continuing professional development (CPD) such as flexibility, skill enhancement, professional development, and technology mediation (Garbe, 2012; Tong et al, 2015; Powell & Bodur, 2019), participant perceptions were analyzed differently due to variations in implementation, technology use, and researcher approach.

Encountered Lots of activity/ programs implemented but can't do it all at once due to other work-related tasks

The table presents the frequency and percentages of the participants leading to the overlapping of activities as one of the challenges in LAC implementation.

The table shows that majority of the participants that constitutes 21 or 95.45 % encountered overlapping activities due to lots of programs and activities implemented. The subthemes and extracted significant statements are shown below.

Table 12. Overlapping of Activities

<i>Subthemes</i>	<i>Responses / Extracted Significant Statements</i>
Time Constraints and Lack of Time Management	Yes, maybe lack of time management.
	Yes, because lack of time and a lot of paper works to do.
	Yes, due to limited time, resources, and conflicting priorities. Managing multiple tasks and prioritizing work is a common challenge in work-related settings, requiring effective time management skills and communication.
Teacher Workload	Yes, one of the problems is that there are many programs that we want to implement, but because of paperwork, we can't do it.
	Sometimes because of work overload.
	Yes, during the time of more events and reports.
	Yes, as a teacher, we have so many tasks not only teaching students but also other work-related, so sometimes we can't do it all in a day.
	Yes, most of the time we are with our learners, which is why we cannot focus on other things.
	Yes, LAC ideas are often helpful and meaningful, but one cannot adapt all strategies at once. It can sometimes be overwhelming, especially when our time is very limited for instructional improvement due to other responsibilities.
	Yes, because new programs may not integrate well with existing curriculum or classroom routines, creating confusion and disruption for students.
Prioritization and Planning	Yes, sometimes there are a lot of good activities or programs, but it's hard to implement them because there are a lot of tasks that need to be done ASAP.
	Yes, it can be overwhelming to try to implement everything at once on top of all the other regular teaching responsibilities. There simply aren't enough hours in the day to manage all these new programs while also delivering core curriculum effectively.
	Yes, it must be one at a time to be able to focus on what to do and what to make.
	Yes, I admit that I can't do it on time, but still manage to do all the programs implemented one at a time.
	Yes, time management is very important in this kind of situation. You have to plan or allocate your time to different tasks or activities. Planning and controlling your time spent on specific tasks allows you to work smarter, be more productive, and efficient.

Theme 4: Overlapping of Activities

The subthemes on overlapping of activities as one of the challenges encountered by the participants are Time Constraints and Lack of Time Management and Teacher Workload. Other suggestions for improvement are focused on Prioritization and Planning for the participants to perform the task-related activities. Data implies that overlapping of activities is still a concern for too many related tasks, too many activities and programs implemented in schools.

The results are consistent with Reaso (2021), who reported that scheduling challenges resulting from several school events and a lack of ICT expertise among certain teachers were the main issues faced during the LAC session's implementation. Similar to this, Vega (2020) observed that the majority of schools concurred that the scheduling of LAC has an impact on their classes, even though it is scheduled around teachers' availability because the allotted time for LAC exceeded two hours; teachers faced difficulties with the output following the LAC activity, which required them to read research papers linked to the concepts that were presented to them. Furthermore, Potane et al. (2018) shown that overlapping schedules and a restricted implementation period were obstacles to LAC implementation.

Redundancy of the LAC Topics

The table shows the frequency and percentages of the redundancy of LAC topics as one of the challenges encountered by the participants in the implementation of LAC.

Data showed that 15 or 68.18 % of the participants stated that there were no redundancy of topics in the LAC whereas 7 or 31.82% of the participants responded that there were redundancy of topics. The subthemes and extracted significant statements are shown below.

Table 13. *Redundancy of LAC topics*

<i>Subthemes</i>	<i>Responses / Extracted Significant Statements</i>
Acknowledgment of Redundancy	"As a teacher, I might have attended some LAC sessions that covered somewhat redundant topics." "Yes. There are times that specific topics will be tackled in other topics because these are interconnected." "Yes, same strategies were discussed although the delivery was different." "Yes, some topics in the LAC sessions are redundant." "Yes, maybe because we need to be refreshed and familiarized again with the topics that have great concerns in our teaching." "Yes, redundancy of topics in a seminar can lead to several reactions from participants like boredom and limited learning."
Suggested Solutions to Address Redundancy	"Here are some ways to address redundancy: pre-session surveys, differentiated sessions, or sharing best practices."
Recognition of Redundancy's Effects	"Redundancy of topics in a seminar can lead to several reactions from participants like boredom and limited learning."
Positive Perspectives on Redundancy	"No, but redundancy of the LAC topics has positive effects, such as self-reflection, and time to reassess your knowledge and skills."
Denial of Redundancy	No, because redundancy is not allowed in LAC sessions." "Not yet. So far all I have attended are on point or related to our topic." "No, it is a different topic of LAC sessions."

Theme 5: Redundancy of LAC Topics

Based on the above-mentioned table, the redundancy of topics in LAC sessions showed the positive and negative feeling of participants. The subthemes emerged were Acknowledgment of Redundancy; Recognition of Redundancy's Effects; Positive Perspectives on Redundancy; Denial of Redundancy; and Suggested Solutions to Address Redundancy. It is noted by the participants that redundancy brings negative reactions such as boredom and limited learning whereas on the positive side creates familiarization and interconnectedness of topics; self-reflection and time to reassess the knowledge and skills. However, it is also noted that the participants provided some ways to address redundancy which includes pre-session surveys, differentiated sessions, or sharing best practices.

In the study of Ganiban (2023) in her study revealed that the participants shared a matrix which is used to construct the training design, which in turn creates the design for the LAC sessions. Before scheduling a LAC session, schools must carefully consider what topics should be covered in the training matrix. The issues, concepts, and discussion subjects need to be well planned. A designated instructor will prepare the matrix by gathering all the requirements that need to be covered on the day of the upcoming LAC session. The school's priorities are outlined in the LAC strategy. Within the training matrix, it is scheduled. Here, the LAC session schedule is established to allow the concerned speaker enough time to get ready.

Meanwhile, the remarks make it very evident that the school carefully arranges its schedule. This demonstrates even more how important planning is when putting on a training or instructional event. It should be noted that well-planned LAC sessions are necessary to train or educate teachers on how to enhance their methods of instruction. According to Elnaga and Imran (2013), companies train

their employees to maximize their potential through long-term planning to prepare them to perform their jobs as intended. An efficient training program is therefore built upon training planning, thus the creation of LAC session design unfavored the redundancy of topics.

Had trouble in internet connection and observed during LAC Sessions

The table shows the profile of the participants regarding their experienced difficulty in internet connection and observed during LAC sessions.

It is reflected in the table that 17 or 77.27% of the participants had trouble in internet connection which was observed during LAC Sessions whereas 5 or 22.73% had no trouble in internet connectivity. Data implies that there were still participants who had trouble in internet connectivity during LAC sessions. The subthemes and extracted significant statements are shown below.

Table 14. Had trouble in internet connection and observed during LAC Sessions

<i>Subthemes</i>	<i>Responses / Extracted Significant Statements</i>
Disruption of Participation and Missed Information	Yes, as a teacher attending virtual LAC sessions, I've definitely experienced difficulties with internet connections and observed others facing them as well. Yes, poor internet connection can lead to disruptions in audio or video transmission, causing participants to miss important instructions, explanations, or discussions. This can result in a loss of engagement and understanding. Sometimes, due to slow Internet connectivity, sometimes this can lead to confusion or misunderstanding about the topic because of the choppy audio or freezing video that prolonged delays while the speaker on the other side continues his discussion.
Frustration and Disengagement	Yes, sometimes it's buffering, and some of our tasks were delayed because of this difficulty. Yes, difficulty in internet connection during seminars can have various reactions from participants, including frustration, disengagement, as participants may lose interest or become distracted while waiting for the connection to improve. Yes, because its buffering, some of our tasks were delayed because of this difficulty.
Observation of Digital Divide	Yes, internet connection is not consistent, therefore digital divide can be observed

Theme 6: Difficulty in Internet Connection During LAC Sessions

The table presents the subthemes emerged along the difficulty in internet connectivity during LAC sessions which includes the Disruption of Participation and Missed Information; Frustration and Disengagement; and Observation of Digital Divide that affects the participation and performance of the participant in attending LAC sessions. The participants were delayed in their task due to miscommunication of shared community of practice. Through this dilemma, it is noted there is an observed gap between participants with access to and effective use of information and communication technologies (ICTs) compared to those who lack them.

Similarly, research by Sitzmann, T., & Ely, D. (2011) explored best practices for designing LAC sessions that are inclusive of those with varying levels of digital access and literacy. This involves offering alternative formats (in-person alongside online), providing clear instructions, and ensuring user-friendly platforms. Also, the Digital Literacy Training discusses the importance of integrating digital literacy training into LAC sessions. This could equip participants with the necessary skills to navigate the online environment and participate effectively while the Community-Based Solutions conducted by Flanagan & Tripp (2017). explore how LAC sessions can leverage community resources to bridge the digital divide. This could involve partnering with libraries, community centers, or schools to offer access to devices and internet connectivity.

Attended LAC sessions objectives that were not clearly stated

The table shows the profile on the non-articulation of LAC session objectives during the sessions.

It presents data that majority of the participants responded that LAC session objectives were not clearly stated during LAC sessions with a frequent count of 18 that constitutes 81.82%. Learning Action Cells (LACs) are collaborative groups within a school or organization that focus on continuous improvement through shared learning and problem-solving. LAC sessions, meetings where these groups convene, play a crucial role in facilitating this process. Data implies that the effectiveness of LAC sessions hinges on clearly articulated objectives. The subthemes and extracted significant statements are shown below.

Table 15. Non-Articulation of LAC Session Objectives

<i>Subthemes</i>	<i>Responses / Extracted Significant Statements</i>
Experience of Unclear Objectives	"Yes, as a teacher, I might have attended LAC sessions where the objectives weren't entirely clear." Yes, because some LAC sessions don't have target objectives."
Challenges of Unclear Objectives	"Unfocused Participation: Without clear objectives, it can be hard to know what's expected from participants and how to best contribute to the discussion." "Unmet Expectations: Attendees might come prepared to address specific areas, only to find out the

Suggestions for Improvement	<p>session focuses on something different. This can lead to a feeling of wasted time or missed opportunities."</p> <p>"Limited Outcomes: If the goals of the session aren't well-defined, it's difficult to measure its effectiveness or ensure it's truly addressing the intended needs."</p> <p>"Pre-session Communication: Distributing agendas or clear descriptions beforehand can ensure everyone understands the learning goals and expected outcomes."</p> <p>"Opening Statements: Starting the session with a clear articulation of objectives reminds participants of the focus and helps guide the discussion."</p> <p>"Interactive Activities: Incorporating activities directly tied to the objectives can help solidify understanding and ensure the session stays on track."</p>
Absence of Unclear Objectives	<p>"No, all objectives are well stated."</p> <p>"No, because objectives should be clearly stated and specific."</p> <p>"No, LAC session is well planned, so the learning objectives and outcome is clear and stated."</p> <p>"Yes, because some objectives were not stated in ABCD format which makes the objectives vague and not so measurable."</p>
Positive Affirmations of Clear Objectives	<p>"Not yet all are clear and demonstrated well."</p>

Theme 7: Non-Articulation of LAC Session Objectives

The subthemes emerged from the extracted statements are Experience of Unclear Objectives; Challenges of Unclear Objectives; and Absence of Unclear Objectives. Data implies that without clear objectives, LAC sessions can become unfocused and inefficient. Participants hinder progress towards achieving meaningful outcomes. Without a defined direction, the group might struggle to achieve any concrete results. Also, the unclear objectives can lead to participant disengagement. If individuals don't understand the purpose of the session, they might feel their time is wasted, leading to lower motivation and a reluctance to actively participate. However, participants responded that with the Positive Affirmations of Clear Objectives, all LAC activities are clear and demonstrated well. It is also suggested by the participants that Pre-session communication should be conducted before the LAC session. It is concluded that clearly articulated objectives are essential for effective LAC sessions. By prioritizing objective development, communication, and monitoring, LAC leaders can ensure that sessions are productive and contribute to the overall goals of the Learning Action Cell.

Addressed learning methodologies and programs depending on the needs of students

The table shows the profile of the participants in addressing learning methodologies and programs depending on the needs of learners. It is noted in the table that participants addressed learning methodologies and programs depending on learners' needs with a frequency of 21 that constitutes 95.45%. whereas only 1 or 4.55 participants did not address the inclusivity of learners along with the methodologies. The following table presents the subthemes and extracted significant statements with the given indicators.

Table 16. *Difficulty in addressing learning methodologies and programs based on the Learners' Needs*

<i>Subthemes</i>	<i>Responses / Extracted Significant Statements</i>
Importance and Commitment to Addressing Student Needs	<p>"Yes, because those needs of learners required immediate solution."</p> <p>"Yes, to provide their needs and learning materials."</p> <p>"Yes, it is important to address the needs of the learners first."</p> <p>"Yes, because it is important for us as educators to assess the needs of our students and select the most suitable learning methodologies and programs accordingly."</p> <p>"Yes especially the students/pupils who need more attention."</p> <p>"Yes, because those needs of learners required immediate solution."</p>
Methods of Addressing Student Needs	<p>"Yes, through trainings or LAC sessions."</p> <p>"Yes, as much as possible or as early as possible, we should know the learning styles of our pupils to address their needs immediately."</p> <p>"Yes, through experience-based learning, learners analyze their experiences by reflecting, evaluating, and reconstructing it in order to draw meaning from it in the light of prior experiences or contextual experience."</p> <p>"Yes. Adapting interactive activities and applying it in my pedagogy really helped me establish collaboration and interface in the classroom especially during online class."</p> <p>"Had difficulty in varied methodologies to address learning needs"</p>
Recognition of Student Diversity	<p>"Yes, most of the time because we have different kinds of learners."</p> <p>"Yes, as a teacher, we should consider the learning methodologies and programs needed by our students; it can vary depending on factors such as their age, learning style, subject matter, and individual needs."</p> <p>"Yes, most of the time because we have different kinds of learners."</p>
Professional Responsibility	<p>"Yes. It's a professional responsibility to all learners."</p>

Theme 8: Difficulty in learning methodologies and programs depending on the needs of students

It is reflected in the table that participants experienced difficulty in varied learning methodologies to address learning needs. By employing a variety of learning methodologies, programs, and interventions, educators can effectively address the diverse needs of their students. Tailoring their approach fosters a more inclusive learning environment where all students can thrive. Indeed, teachers need commitment and professional accountability to address learners' needs.

Conclusions

From the salient findings, the conclusions drawn are as follows:

1. LAC sessions empower teachers in the district to take ownership of their professional development by focusing on school-specific needs along Learner Diversity and Student Inclusion; Content and Pedagogy; Assessment and Reporting; 21st-Century Skills and ICT Integration; and Curriculum Contextualization, Localization. They also fostered a collaborative environment among teachers, allowing them to share best practices and address common challenges.
2. Addressing the challenges in implementing LAC in the district strengthens the effectiveness of LAC sessions, leading to continued professional growth for teachers and ultimately, improved student learning outcomes.

Based on the conclusions, the recommendations are as follows:

1. The schools in the district shall follow the mechanisms in implementing its LAC sessions through a localized LAC framework. Notably, the mechanisms being followed by the school conform to the principles of designing training programs from analysis of needs to evaluation of the training.
2. The schools in the district shall consider the following: (a) explore flexible scheduling options for LAC sessions, considering shorter, more frequent meetings and or blended collaboration tools. (b) implement strategies to encourage active participation, such as rotating leadership roles or assigning specific tasks to each member. (c) establish clear and measurable goals for each LAC session, ensuring they align with the district's overall professional development plan. (d) regularly share successful outcomes from LAC sessions to motivate teachers and showcase the program's effectiveness; (e) allocate resources to support LAC sessions, such as professional development materials or guest speakers on relevant topics.
3. The emergence of implementing Learning Action Cell (LAC) sessions calls for the conduct of scientific study that shall investigate it in the light of various research variables. As such, conducting similar studies in a wider coverage is needed in which the output of the study should be implemented and evaluated in terms of its effectiveness.

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